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ABSTRACT

The coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic has attracted greater attention than ever before to the problems of immunopathology of human diseases, many of which are reflected in the study of neurodegenerative diseases. COVID-19 has clearly shown that one of the most significant targets of the RNA virus SARS-CoV-2 is the nervous system. Of particular interest is the relationship between COVID-19 and neurodegenerative diseases, including Parkinson's disease (PD). Parkinson's disease, according to its classical definition, is a chronic, progressive neurodegenerative disease. Currently, diagnosis is possible only with the development of motor symptoms (stiffness, oligo-, brady-, akinesia, rest tremor). The new coronavirus infection SARS-CoV-2 has neurotropic properties, and to date, cases of the development of delirium, meningitis, encephalitis, and acute transverse myelitis at the onset and/or against the background of the advanced course of COVID-19 have been described. Coronavirus can lead to an excessive, unregulated immune response in the host body - cytokine release syndrome. Increasingly, information is being heard that this type of immune response is an integral part of the development of target organ dysfunction and one of the main factors of morbidity. Immunological mechanisms in patients who have had Covid-19 have unique features. Uncontrolled production of cytokines by innate and acquired immune cells leads to the development of a "cytokine storm". This work characterizes changes in the amount of immunological cytokines - interleukin-6

(IL-6) in Parkinson's disease. The impact of Covid-19 infection on the clinical course of Parkinson's disease, as well as the risk factor for the development of parkinsonism, is discussed.

Keywords: Covid-19 infection, Parkinson's disease, "cytokine storm", interleukin-6, ferritin

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ИЗМЕНЕНИЕ УРОВНИ ИНТЕРЛЕЙКИНА-6 У БОЛЬНЫХ ПРЕНЕСШИХ COVID-19 С БОЛЕЗНЬЮ ПАРКИНСОНА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Пандемия коронавирусной болезни (COVID-19) привлекла более пристальное, чем прежде, внимание к проблемам иммунопатологии болезней человека, многие из которых нашли отражение при изучении нейродегенеративных заболеваний. COVID-19 со всей определенностью показала, что одной из наиболее значимых мишеней РНК-содержащего вируса SARS-CoV-2 является нервная система. Особый интерес вызывает изучение взаимосвязи между COVID-19 и нейродегенеративными заболеваниями, в том числе болезнью Паркинсона (БП). Болезнь Паркинсона, согласно своему классическому определению, - это хроническое прогрессирующее нейродегенеративное заболевание. В настоящее время постановка диагноза возможна только при развитии моторных симптомов (скованность, олиго-, бради-, акинезия, тремор покоя). Новая коронавирусная инфекция SARS-CoV-2 обладает нейротропными свойствами, и к настоящему времени описаны случаи развития делирия, менингита, энцефалита, острого поперечного миелита в дебюте и/или на фоне развернутого течения COVID-19. Коронавирус способен приводить к излишнему, нерегулируемому иммунному ответу в организме хозяина — синдрому высвобождения цитокинов. Всё чаще звучит информация о том, что данный вид иммунного ответа является неотъемлемой частью развития дисфункции органов-мишеней и одним из основных факторов заболеваемости. Иммунологические механизмы у больных перенесших Covid-19 имеют уникальные особенности. Бесконтрольная продукция цитокинов клетками врожденного и приобретенного иммунитета приводит к развитию «цитокинового шторма». В данной работе охарактеризованы изменения количества иммунологических цитокинов- интерлейкина-6 (ИЛ-6) при болезни Паркинсона. Обсуждаются влияния инфекции Covid-19 на клиническое течение болезни Паркинсона, а также факторе риска развития паркинсонизма.

Ключевые слова: инфекция Covid-19, болезнь Паркинсона, “цитокиновый шторм”, интерлейкин-6, ферритин.

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COVID-19 O'TKAZGAN PARKINSON KASALLIGI BILAN OG'RIGAN BEMORLARDA INTERLEYKIN-6 MIQDORINING O'ZGARISH DARAJALARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Koronavirus kasalligi (COVID-19) pandemiyasi inson kasalliklarining immunopatologiyasi muammolariga har qachongidan ham ko'proq e'tibor qaratishni talab etdi, ularning aksariyati neyrodegenerativ kasalliklarni o'rganishda aks ettirilgan. RNK saqlochi SARS-CoV-2 virusining eng muhim nishon tizimlaridan biri, bu asab tizimi ekanligini aniq ko'rsatdi. COVID-19 va neyrodegenerativ kasalliklar, jumladan Parkinson kasalligi (PD) o'rtasidagi munosabatlar alohida qiziqishlarni uyg'otadi. Parkinson kasalligi, uning klassik ta'rifiga ko'ra, surunkali, progressiv neyrodegenerativ kasallik hisoblanadi. Hozirgi vaqtda diagnostika qilish faqat motor belgilari (qotib qolish, oligo- va bradikineziya, tinch holatda tremor bo'lishi) rivojlanishiga binoan aniqlanishi mumkin. Yangi SARS-CoV-2 infeksiyasi neyrotrop xususiyatlarga ega va hozirgi kunga qadar COVID-19 ning boshida va/yoki eng rivojlangan davri fonida deliriy, meningit, ensefalit va o'tkir ko'ndalang mielit rivojlanishi holatlari kuzatildi. Koronavirus xo'jayin organizmida haddan tashqari, tartibga solib bo'lmaydigan immun reaksiyaga - sitokinlar ajralishi sindromiga olib kelishi mumkin. Immunitetning ushbu turi nishon organlar disfunktsiyasi rivojlanishining ajralmas qismi va kasallikning asosiy omillaridan biri ekanligi haqida ma'lumotlar tobora ko'payib bormoqda. Covid-19 o'tkazgan bemorlarda immunologik mexanizmlar o'ziga xos bo'lgan xususiyatlarga ega. Tug'ma va orttirilgan immunitet hujayralari tomonidan nazorat qilinmaydigan sitokinlarning ishlab chiqarilishi «sitokinli bo'ron» rivojlanishiga olib keladi. Ushbu ishda Parkinson kasalligida immunologik sitokinlar - interleykin-6 (IL-6) miqdorining o'zgarishlarini tavsiflaydi. Ushbu ishda Covid-19 infeksiyasining Parkinson kasalligining klinik kechishiga ta'siri, shuningdek, parkinsonizm rivojlanishi uchun xavf omili muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Covid-19 infeksiyasi, Parkinson kasalligi, "sitokinli shtorm", interleykin-6, ferritin.

Kirish. Koronavirus infeksiyasi (Covid-19) pandemiya ko'rinishida butun yer yuzi mamlakatlari aholisini larzaga solgan o'ta dolzarb bo'lgan muammodir. Dunyoning biror bir mamlakati yo'qki, ushbu virus kirib bormagan bo'lsa. Ko'pchilik bemorlarning o'limiga sabab bo'ldi, ba'zi bemorlarda esa ma'lum bir kasalliklarning kechishini og'irlashtirdi, nogironlik holatlarini kuchaytirdi va shu borada keskin ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy muammolarni barqarorlashtirdi [1,5,7,8,10,11,12,13,17].

Covid-19 infeksiyasi organizmning barcha tizimlari qatori markaziy asab tizimiga ham kuchli ta'sir qildi, jumladan bosh miya qon tomir kasalliklari, periferik asab tizimi kasalliklari, epilepsiya va neyrodegenerativ kasalliklar rivojlanishiga turtki bo'ldi. Shu bilan bir qatorda xavf omili sifatida parkinsonizm rivojlanishiga olib keldi. Parkinson kasalligi (PK) bilan og'rigan bemorlarda esa kasallikning kechishini jadallashtirdi va nogironlik holatlarini turg'unlashtirdi [2,3,4,6,9,15,18].

Covid-19 o'tkazgan bemorlarda immunologik mexanizmlar o'ziga xos bo'lgan xususiyatlarga ega. Tug'ma va orttirilgan immunitet hujayralari tomonidan nazorat qilinmaydigan sitokinlarning ishlab chiqarilishi «sitokinli bo'ron» rivojlanishiga olib keladi. Koronaviruslarning membranasi 4 ta komponentdan iborat bo'ladi: boshqoq oqsili (S), parda oqsili (E), membrana oqsili (M) va nukleokapsid oqsil. SARS-CoV va SARS-CoV-2 viruslari uchun S oqsil asosiy determinant patogenlik xususiyatiga ega, shuningdek antitelolarning tarqalishi va neytralizatsiyasi uchun nishon hisoblanadi. Shuning uchun ham S oqsil immunologik javob qismi hisoblanib, vaksina ishlab chiqarishga ham qaratilgan mezondir. Angiotenzin fermentlari (Angiotensin-convertingenzyme-2, ACE2) bilan bog'lanib oladi va purinni parchalab tashlaydi. Undan tashqari S oqsil tarkibidagi

retseptor bog'lovchi domen ((Receptor-binding domain, RBD) SARS-CoV-2 maxsus antitelolarining ishlab chiqarilishiga javob beradi. Virus angaptativ immunitet hujayralarida kuzatilishi mumkin va ushbu jarayonda T-limfotsitlar alohida o'rin tutadi. T-xelperlar (1-17 sinf) ichida IL-1, IL-6 va TNF- α muhim ahamiyatga ega. TNF α , IL-1 β , IL-2, IL-6, IFN α , IFN β , IFN γ , MCP-1 (monocyte chemoattractant protein) va granulodar-makrofagal kolonin faktor (GM-CSF) ko'plab ishlab chiqarila boshlaydi. IL-6 va (GM-CSF faktor esa «sitokinli shtorm» rivojlanishining turtki omili hisoblanadi [16,19].

B.J. Huang va hamm. (2020-yil) Covid-19 o'tkazgan bemorlarda yallig'lanish faktorlarini o'rgandilar. IL-1 β , IL-1R α , IL-7, IL-8, IL-9, IL-10, fibroblastlar o'sish faktori (Fibroblast growth factor, FGF), GM-CSF, G-CSF, IFN γ , IFN- γ indutsibel protein (Interferon- γ -inducible protein, IP10), MCP1, makrofag yallig'lanish protein 1 α (Macrophage inflammatory protein 1 α , MIP1A), faktor rosta trombositlar -o'sish faktori (Platelet derived growth factor, PDGF), TNF α , tomirlar endoteliysi o'sish faktori (Vascular endothelial growth factor, VEGF) ichida , IL-2, IL-7, IL-10, G-CSF, IP10, MCP1, MIP1A, TNF α yuqori konsentratsiyada bo'lishi kuzatilgan [18,20,21].

Parkinson kasalligida immunologik sitokinlar miqdorining o'zgarishi to'g'risida ilmiy adabiyotlarda ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Covid-19 infeksiyasi va PK o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik to'g'risida esa juda ko'plab qarama-qarshi fikrlar mavjud. Ferritin koronavirusdan keyingi davrda muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan marker hisoblanadi va PK klinik kechishiga ta'sir qilishi, shuningdek parkinsonizm rivojlanishi uchun xavf omili to'g'risida ham ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Shu nuqtai nazardan biz, Covid-19 o'tkazgan va o'tkazmagan bemorlarda interleykin-6 va ferritin miqdorining o'zgarishini solishtirma tahlil qilishni maqsad qilib oldik.

Tadqiqot materiali va usullari. Parkinson kasalligida interleykin-6 miqdorining o'zgarish darajalarini solishtirish uchun umumiy 120 nafar bemorda, jumladan PK bilan og'rikan 90 nafar bemor va 30 nafar PK kuzatilmagan bemorlarning qon zardobi tekshiruvdan o'tkazildi. Asosiy guruhdagi PK bilan og'rikan bemorlarning 48 nafari (53,3%) erkak va 42 nafari (46,7%) ayollarni tashkil qildi. Nazorat guruhi ham shunga mos ravishda 16 nafari (53,3%) erkaklar va 14 nafari (46,7%) ayollardan iborat bo'ldi. PK bilan og'rikan erkak bemorlarning yoshi 22-70 yoshgacha bo'lib, o'rtacha $46,6 \pm 9,8$ va ayollarning yoshi 28-78 yoshgacha bo'lib, o'rtacha $53,7 \pm 11,9$ yoshni tashkil etdi. Kasallik davomiyligi erkaklarda $5,1 \pm 3,6$ yilni tashkil etgan bo'lsa, ayollarda esa $6,5 \pm 4,8$ yilni tashkil etdi.

PK bilan og'rikan asosiy guruhdagi bemorlar 2 ta guruhga ajratildi: 1-guruh Covid-19 o'tkazgan PK bilan og'rikan bemorlar 45 nafari (50%) va Covid-19 o'tkazmagan PK bilan og'rikan bemorlar 45 nafari (50%). Har ikkala guruhdagi bemorlar kasallik klinik shakllari va bosqichlari bo'yicha guruhlarga ajratildi. 1-guruh PK bilan og'rikan bemorlardan 16 nafari (35,6%) akinetik-rigid shakli bilan og'rikan bemorlar, 14 nafari (31,1%) titroq shakli bilan og'rikan bemorlar va 15 nafari (33,3%) kasallikning aralash shakli bilan og'rikan beorlardan iborat bo'ldi. Barcha guruhdagi bemorlar yoshi va jinsiga qarab turib bir xil yaqin miqdorda olindi. Og'ir kasalligi va qo'shimcha patologiyasi bo'lgan bemorlar tadqiqotimizga kiritilmadi. Kasallik bosqichlari bo'yicha solishtirilganda 1-guruhdagi bemorlarning 13 nafari (28,9%) 1-bosqich, 14 nafari (31,1%) 2-bosqich, 13 nafari (28,9%) 3-bosqich va 5 nafari (11,1%) 4-bosqichdagi PK bilan og'rikan bemorlardir. 2-guruh Covid-19 o'tkazmagan PK bilan og'rikan bemorlardan 15 nafari (33,3%) akinetik-rigid shakli bilan og'rikan bemorlar, 16 nafari (35,6%) titroq shakli bilan og'rikan bemorlar va 14 nafari (31,1%) kasallikning aralash shakli bilan og'rikan beorlardan iborat bo'ldi. Barcha guruhdagi bemorlar yoshi va jinsiga qarab turib bir xil yaqin miqlorda olindi. Kasallik bosqichlari bo'yicha solishtirilganda 1-guruhdagi bemorlarning 14 nafari (31,1%) 1-bosqich, 16 nafari (35,6%) 2-bosqich, 15 nafari (33,3%) 3-bosqich PK bilan og'rikan bemorlardir.

Bizning tadqiqotimizda qon zardobidagi glial IL-6 miqdori immunoferment analiz (IFA) usuli bilan tekshirildi. Buning uchun belgilab olingan bemorlarning tirsak vena qon tomiridan 10,0 ml miqdorda qon olindi va 10 min davomida minutiga 2000 marta tezlikda sentrifuga qilindi. Qon zardobi maxsus probirkalarga solinib muzlatgichda 30⁰ da muzlatilgan holatda saqlandi.

Tadqiqot natijalari. Olingan natijalar shuni ko'rsatmoqdaki, PK bilan og'rikan umumiy 90 nafar bemoraning qon zardobidagi IL-6 miqdori o'rtacha $15,49 \pm 4,4$ pg/ml ni tashkil etdi, nazorat

guruhdagi PK bilan og‘rigan bemorlarda esa ushbu ko‘rsatkich $5,78 \pm 3,8$ pg/ml ekanligi ma‘lum bo‘ldi. IL-6 miqdori asosiy guruhda nazorat guruhga nisbatan deyarli 2,7 barobar oshganligi ma‘lum bo‘ldi ($p < 0,001$). Olingan natijalarni shu bilan izohlash mumkinki, IL-6 miqdori birinchidan Covid-19 infeksiyasi tufayli oshgan bo‘lishi mumkin, shuningdek PK uchun ham nospesifik immunologik faktor bo‘lishi mumkin.

Shu nuqtai nazardan keyingi navbatda asosiy guruhdagi Covid-19 o‘tkazgan va o‘tkazmagan bemorlarda bemorlarda IL-6 miqdorini analiz qildik. 1-guruhdagi Covid-19 o‘tkazgan bemorlar qon zardobi tarkibida IL-6 miqdori $21,37 \pm 5,5$ pg/ml ekanligi ma‘lum bo‘ldi va nazorat guruhga nisbatan ishonchli farq qildi, $p \leq 0,001$. 2-guruhdagi Covid-19 o‘tkazmagan bemorlar qon zardobi tarkibida IL-6 miqdori esa $12,91 \pm 4,7$ pg/ml ekanligi ma‘lum bo‘ldi va nazorat guruhga nisbatan ishonchli farq qildi, $p \leq 0,001$. Shuningdek 1-guruh Covid-19 o‘tkazgan va 2-guruh Covid-19 o‘tkazmagan bemorlar qon zardobi tarkibidagi IL-6 miqdori ishonchli ravishda keskin farq qildi, $p \leq 0,001$.

Keyingi bosqichda biz har ikkala Covid-19 o‘tkazgan va o‘tkazmagan bemorlar qon zardobi tarkibidagi IL-6 miqdorini kasallik klinik shakllari bo‘yicha solishtirishni lozim topdik. 1-guruhdagi PK akinetik-rigid shakli bilan og‘rigan bemorlar qon zardobi tarkibida IL-6 miqdori $24,7 \pm 6,2$ pg/ml, PK titroq shaklida $18,6 \pm 4,3$ pg/ml va aralash shaklida $19,6 \pm 6,2$ pg/ml ekanligi ma‘lum bo‘ldi. Solishtirish natijasi shundan iboratki, kasallikning titroq va aralash shakli o‘rtasida ishonchli fark kuo‘zatilmadi, $p \geq 0,05$. 2-guruhdagi Covid-19 o‘tkazmagan bemor kasallik klinik shakllari bo‘yicha solishtirilganda, kasallikning akinetik-rigid shaklida $15,32 \pm 4,8$ pg/ml, kasallikning titroq shaklida $12,5 \pm 6,1$ pg/ml va kasallikning aralash shaklida $10,1 \pm 4,4$ pg/ml ekanligi qayd qilindi, nazorat guruhga nisbatan ishonchli farq kuzatilsada, kasallikning aralash va titroq shakllari o‘rtasida keskin ishonchli farq kuzatilmadi. Akinetik shakli bilan solishtirilganda, asosiy 1-guruhdagi bemorlarda nisbatan ishonchli farq keskin namoyon bo‘ldi, 1-jadval.

1-jadval.

Kasallik klinik shakllari bo‘yicha IL-6 miqdorining solishtirma tahlili

Kasallik klinik shakllari	Covid-19 o‘tkazganlar	Covid-19 o‘tkazmaganlar	Ishonchli farq
Akinetik-rigid	$24,7 \pm 6,2^{**}$	$15,32 \pm 4,8^{**}$	$p \leq 0,001$
Titroq	$18,6 \pm 4,3^*$	$12,5 \pm 6,1^{***}$	$p \leq 0,05$
Aralash	$19,6 \pm 6,2$	$10,1 \pm 4,4$	$p \leq 0,001$

Izoh:-** - ishonchli farq $p \leq 0,001$, *** - ishonchli farq $p \leq 0,05$, *- ishonchli farq aniqlanmagan.

Keyingi bosqichda biz har ikkala Covid-19 o‘tkazgan va o‘tkazmagan bemorlar qon zardobi tarkibidagi IL-6 miqdorini kasallik bosqichlari bo‘yicha solishtirishni lozim topdik. 1-guruhdagi PK 1-bosqich bilan og‘rigan bemorlar qon zardobi tarkibida IL-6 miqdori $13,8 \pm 4,2$, 2-bosqich bemorlar qon zardobi tarkibida $21,8 \pm 5,1$ pg/ml va 3-bosqich aralash shaklida $26,7 \pm 5,3$ pg/ml pg/ml ekanligi ma‘lum bo‘ldi. Solishtirish natijasi shundan iboratki, kasallikning barcha bosqichlari o‘rtasida ishonchli farq kuzatildi, $p \leq 0,001$. 2-guruhdagi Covid-19 o‘tkazmagan bemorlar kasallik bosqichlari solishtirilganda, kasallikning 1-bosqichida $12,1 \pm 5,2$ pg/ml, kasallikning 2-bosqichida $16,45 \pm 4,8$ pg/ml va kasallikning 3-bosqichida $19,5 \pm 5,7$ pg/ml ekanligi qayd qilindi, nazorat guruhga nisbatan ishonchli farq kuzatilsada, kasallikning 1-va 2-bosqichlar o‘rtasida keskin ishonchli farq kuzatilmadi. Har ikkala guruh solishtirilganda, asosiy 1-guruhdagi bemorlarda nisbatan ishonchli farq keskin namoyon bo‘ldi, 2-jadval.

2-jadval.

Kasallik klinik bosqichlari bo‘yicha IL-6 miqdorining solishtirma tahlili

Kasallik klinik shakllari	Covid-19 o‘tkazganlar	Covid-19 o‘tkazmaganlar	Ishonchli farq
1-bosqich	$13,8 \pm 4,2$	$12,1 \pm 5,2^{**}$	$p \leq 0,001$
2-bosqich	$21,8 \pm 5,1$	$16,45 \pm 4,8^{**}$	$p \geq 0,05$
3-bosqich	$26,7 \pm 5,3$	$19,5 \pm 5,7^{***}$	$p \leq 0,05$
4-bosqich	$29,1 \pm 6,5$	-	

	$p \leq 0,001$	$p \leq 0,05$	
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Izoh:-** - ishonchli farq $p \leq 0,001$, *** - ishonchli farq $p \leq 0,05$,

*- ishonchli farq aniqlanmagan.

Xulosalar. Yuqorida olingan natijalarni shunday izohlash mumkinki, IL-6 miqdorining oshib borishi immunoglobulin G miqdorining oshib borishi bilan parallel bog'liqdir. Covid-19 infeksiyasidan keyingi davrdagi o'zgarishlar bemorlar qon zardobi tarkibidagi sitokinlar miqdori, jumladan IL-6 darajasi bilan bog'liqdir. Ushbu sitokin miqdorining oshishi PK bilan og'rikan bemorlarda kasallikning og'irlik darajalarini ko'rsatishi mumkin. Kasallikning akinetik-rigid shakli nisbatan titroq shaklga qaraganda og'irroq kechadi va bu yuqori darajadagi dofamin defitsiti bilan bog'liqdir. Shuning uchun ham PK bilan og'rikan bemorlar Covid-19 infeksiyasini o'tkazsa kasallik belgilari og'irlashib boradi, titroq shakllarga qaraganda akinetik-rigid shaklida kuchayib boradi. Kasallik bosqichlari bo'yicha solishtirilganda 1-bosqichga nisbatan 2-bosqich, 3-bosqich va 4-bosqichlarda yanada yuqori darajada namoyon bo'ladi. Covid-19 infeksiyasi PK bilan og'rikan bemorlarda kasallik bosqichlarini ham transformatsiyasiga tez o'zgartirib yuboradi, yengil bosqichlardan og'ir bosqichlargacha chuqurlashtiradi. IL-6 Covid-19 o'tkazgan PK bilan og'rikan bemorlarni og'irlik darajalarini baholashda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi va shunga mos ravishda differensial yondashuvni talab qiladi.

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